

“ReadMe” – or – “How to document your data?”

The basics of the “ReadMe”:

- provide a meta-data description of your project, so that you and other have a glimpse of idea what's inside your folder/files/repository – any information is better than nothing
- root folder should have generic `ReadMe` followed by descriptive `ReadMe` in each subfolder
- in the simplest way provide `ASCII` text file describing your work avoiding `.docx` or `.odt`
- it is usually a simple plain-text file called `READ.ME`, `README.TXT`, `ReadMe.md` or `README`
- often simple `ReadMe.md` formatted in the human readable Markdown markup language^[1]
- some guidance can be found in Ref.^[2] and a list of best practice `READMEs` in Ref.^[3]

The contents of the “ReadMe”:

- rule of thumb: document relevant details about data collection, processing, and analysis
- minimum information: title, creator, contact, file naming convention, folder structure, description of data (5W1H+R^[4]: What? When? Where? Who? Why? How? +Relationship), license, and ...as much information as possible

Where to go from here: For interoperability of metadata use the Dublin Core standard^[5] with XML-schema or JSON-LD^[6].

References:

[1] <https://daringfireball.net/projects/markdown/syntax>

[2] <https://www.makeareadme.com/>

[3] <https://github.com/matiassingers/awesome-readme>

[4] Subramaniam, Pranav / Ma, Yintong / Li, Chi / Mohanty, Ipsita / Fernandez, Raul Castro Comprehensive and Comprehensible Data Catalogs: The What, Who, Where, When, Why, and How of Metadata Management 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.07532>

[5] https://dublincore.org/resources/userguide/creating_metadata/

[6] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON-LD>

README.md

```
# Title
Paper/Project
(The name given to the paper/project/files.)

# Creator
Manu Musterperson
(Who created the resource?)

# Creator:ORCID
0000-0001-2345-6789
(ORCID identifier of the Creator)

# Creator:Email
musterperson@domain.de
(email identifier of the Creator)

# Publisher
Institute of Fancy Science
Department of Amazing Science
Imaginary Street 42
D-01234 ImaginaryTown
Country
(The department/institute responsible in which the resource have been created.)

# Description
Exemplary test case to verify the simulation tools and compare to the experiment.
Data have been published at Zenodo under CC-BY 4.0, see
https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.XYZ .
(A textual description of the content of the resource.)

# Subject
* Experiment Data
* Analytic Data
* Abbreviation: NMR, SAXS
* (Phrase\Keywords describing the content of the resource.)

# Date
2023-10-17
(A date associated with the creation or availability of the resource. Recommended format:
YYYY-MM-DD)

# Format
* dat
* docx
* pdf
* (The data format to identify the software and possibly hardware that might be needed to
display or operate the resource).

# Tools
Tool01XYZ hasURL https://github.com/FakeUser/FakeProject/releases/tag/v1.0
Tool01XYZ hasDependency https://github.com/FakeProjectDependsOn/releases/tag/v2.2.2
Tool01XYZ hasDOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.ZYX
(Refer to your (post-)processing tools, e.g. URL or git hash)

# Type
Simulation
(The category of the resource, such as experiment, simulation, report, text, draft,
image...)

# Coverage
2019-2024
(Temporal coverage is typically a period for acquiring the data.)

# Source
PhD-Thesis hasDOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.ABC
(Information about a second resource from which the present resource is derived.)

# Relation
Experiment IsPartOf PhD-Thesis
(An identifier to provide a relationship from source to the present resource,
e.g. IsVersionOf, IsReplacedBy, IsPartOf, IsReferencedBy)

# License
CC-BY 4.0 hasURL https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
(A rights management statement of the resource, e.g. license for publishing and sharing.)
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- ✓ structured layout with minimal information including relational identifiers (similar to [rdf-schema](#))
 - ✓ simple parsing and machine processing is possible between '#' section to archive interoperability
 - ✓ minimal standard in analogy to Dublin Core identifiers